

EFFECTS OF NON-FICKIAN MOISTURE DIFFUSION IN POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: This article concerns the effects of non-Fickian water diffusion in fiber-reinforced polymeric composites. The departure from classical diffusion is attributed to the time-dependent response of the polymer, akin to viscoelastic mechanical response.

The purpose of the present work is to propose a methodology to reduce non-Fickian moisture weight-gain data in a manner which enables the evaluation of the diffusion coefficient and moisture profiles across the thickness of composite laminates. The evaluation of those moisture profiles is essential to the computation of residual stresses within composite laminates.

It is demonstrated that in some circumstances the non-Fickian moisture profiles result in residual hygro-thermal stresses which differ by about 25% from predictions based upon classical diffusion.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that polymeric composites absorb water when exposed to wet environments, which results in residual hydral stresses analogous to residual thermal stresses in composite laminates.

In many circumstances it has been observed that moisture weight-gain data depart significantly from the characteristic format predicted by the linear diffusion model ("Fick's Law").

The above departures can be attributed to various causes, such as non-linear diffusion, internal damage, spatially inhomogeneous degrees of resin cure, etc. However, it appears that the simplest interpretation for non-Fickian behavior is provided by considering time-dependent processes within the polymer which are akin to mechanical creep.

Accordingly, it has been shown [1] that upon considering a Gibbs-free energy function $\phi = \phi(\sigma_{ij}, C, T, \gamma_r)$, where σ_{ij} , C and T denote stress, moisture content and temperature while γ_r ($r = 1, \dots, N$) represent internal degrees of freedom of molecular motion, these motions being resisted by viscous-like internal forces, it is possible to express the chemical potential within the polymer by a Prony series analogous to the representation of the creep compliance.

The above result suggests that the boundary condition for a diffusion process within polymers and polymeric composites which are exposed to constant ambient environment should take the form

$$C(\underline{x}; t) = C_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N C_i (1 - e^{-\beta_i t}) \quad (\underline{x} \text{ on boundary}) \quad (1)$$

Equation 1 implies that the internal processes within the polymer require time before the establishment of equilibrium with a prescribed ambient humidity condition.

2. MOISTURE CONTENT ANALYSIS

Consider a one-dimensional diffusion process into an initially dry plate of thickness $2L$. In view of the above-mentioned time dependent molecular processes, the diffusion process is governed by

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} \quad t > 0, \quad -L \leq z \leq L \quad (2)$$

$$C(z, 0) = 0 \quad -L \leq z \leq L \quad (3)$$

$$C(\pm L, t) = C_0 + \sum_{n=1}^N C_n (1 - e^{-\beta_n t}) H(t) \quad t > 0 \quad (4)$$

In the above equations C denotes moisture content, D is the coefficient of moisture diffusion, z is the thickness coordinate, t is time, and $H(t)$ the Heaviside unit step function.

The solution for $C(z, t)$ is well known [2]. It reads

$$C(z, t) = C_0 C_H(z, t) + \sum_{n=1}^N C_n \tilde{C}(z, t; \beta_n) \quad (5)$$

where

$$C_H(z, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \left[\operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{2n+1-z/L}{2\sqrt{t^*}} \right) + \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{2n+1+z/L}{2\sqrt{t^*}} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{C}(z, t; \beta) = & 1 - \exp(-\beta t) \cdot \frac{\cos z\sqrt{\beta D}}{\cos L\sqrt{\beta D}} \\ & - \frac{16\beta L^2}{\pi} \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \exp \left\{ -[(2n+1)\pi/2]^2 t^* \right\}}{(2n+1)[4\beta L^2 - D\pi(2n+1)^2]} \cos \frac{(2n+1)\pi z}{2L} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The corresponding weight gain $M(t)$ is given by [2]

$$M(t) = C_0 M_H(t) + \sum_{n=1}^N C_n \widehat{M}(t; \beta_n) \quad (8)$$

where

$$M_H(t) = 4L\sqrt{t^*} \cdot \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \operatorname{ierfc} \left(\frac{n}{\sqrt{\pi}} \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

and

$$\widehat{M}(t; \beta) = 2L \cdot \left\{ 1 - \exp(-\beta t) \sqrt{\frac{D}{\beta L^2}} \tan \sqrt{\frac{\beta L^2}{D}} \right. \\ \left. - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\exp\{-(2n+1)\pi/2\}^2 t^*\}}{(2n+1)^2 \left\{ 1 - (2n+1)^2 \left[D\pi^2 / (4\beta L^2) \right] \right\}} \right\} \quad (10)$$

In Equations 6, 7, 9 and 10, $t^* = Dt/L^2$.

Employing rather straightforward curve fitting routines [3] it is possible to obtain the "best" values for C_0 , C_n and β_n ($n = 1, \dots, N$) which match the non-Fickian experimental total weight gain data to within a desirable tolerance. To demonstrate a specific case of non-Fickian diffusion we employ weight-gain data for Fiberite T300/1014 composite [4]. Employing our routine it was possible to obtain the fit shown in Figure 1 by means of a seven-term Prony series with $C_0 = 0.7$ and $N = 7$, $C_1 = 0.098605$, $C_2 = 0.021929$, $C_3 = -0.083097$, $C_4 = 0.27450$, $C_5 = -0.55194$, $C_6 = 1.7834$, $C_7 = -1.5819$ and $\beta_1 = 1/10$, $\beta_2 = 1/50$, $\beta_3 = 1/100$, $\beta_4 = 1/500$, $\beta_5 = 1/1000$, $\beta_6 = 1/5000$, $\beta_7 = 1/10000$ (β in hours⁻¹). For future reference the data in Figure 1 are bracketed by an "upper" and a "lower" Fickian curves, which abide by the strictures of linear Fickian weight gain predictions.

3. DETERMINATION OF D, THE COEFFICIENT OF MOISTURE DIFFUSION

For the linear Fickian case it is possible to infer on the value of D according to [5]

$$D = \frac{\pi}{16} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{[M_H(t)]^2}{t} \quad (11)$$

The above expression is not valid for non-Fickian circumstances.

Employing the hypothesis that non-Fickian behavior is attributable to the time-dependent response of the polymeric material, as reflected in boundary condition [4], we rewrite the latter expression as follows

$$C(\pm L, t) = C_0 [1 + f(t)] H(t) \quad (12)$$

with $f(0) = 0$

Thus

$$M(t) = C_0 \left\{ M_H(t) + \int_0^t M_H(t-\tau) \frac{df(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \right\} \quad (13)$$

Let $\tilde{g}(s)$ denote the Carson transform of $g(t)$, namely $\tilde{g}(s) = s \int_0^\infty e^{-st} g(t) dt$ then, in view of Equation 13 we have $\tilde{M}(s) = C_0 \tilde{M}_H(s) [1 + \tilde{f}(s)]$ whence

$$\tilde{f}(s) = \frac{1}{C_0} \frac{\tilde{M}(s)}{\tilde{M}_H(s)} - 1 \quad (14)$$

The expression for $\tilde{M}_H(s)$ is well known [2], namely

$$\tilde{M}_H(s) = 2\sqrt{\frac{D}{s}} \tanh \sqrt{\frac{s}{D}} L \quad (15)$$

and by hypothesis $f(t)$, and thereby $\tilde{f}(s)$, is independent of the plate's thickness L . Therefore, consider two sets of weight gain data $M(t;L_1)$ and $M(t;L_2)$ associated with thicknesses L_1 and L_2 , respectively. Equation 14 yields

$$\frac{\tilde{M}(s; L_1; D)}{\tilde{M}(s; L_2; D)} = \frac{\tilde{M}_H(s; L_1)}{\tilde{M}_H(s; L_2)} \quad (16)$$

Note that Equation 16 contains the unknown D alone and does not include $\tilde{f}(s)$ and C_0 . This feature enables the determination of D by the best fit to non-Fickian weight gain data obtained for plates of two distinct thicknesses L_1 and L_2 . Details are given in Reference [3].

4. MOISTURE EFFECTS ON RESIDUAL STRESSES

An assessment of the effects of non-Fickian moisture profiles, which correspond to the weight-gain data shown in Figure 1, on residual hydro-thermal stresses in composite laminates is provided by considering the case of a $[0_2^\circ/90_2^\circ]_s$ lay-up. The basic stress-strain relations for cross-ply lay-ups are according to Reference [6]:

For the 0° layers,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x(z, t) = & Q_L [\epsilon_x^0(t) + \varepsilon \kappa_x(t) - \alpha_L \Delta T - \beta_L C_e(z, t)] \\ & + Q_{LT} [\epsilon_y^0(t) + \varepsilon \kappa_y(t) - \alpha_T \Delta T - \beta_T C_e(z, t)] \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y(z, t) = & Q_{LT} [\epsilon_x^0(t) + \varepsilon \kappa_x(t) - \alpha_L \Delta T - \beta_L C_e(z, t)] \\ & + Q_T [\epsilon_y^0(t) + \varepsilon \kappa_y(t) - \alpha_T \Delta T - \beta_T C_e(z, t)] \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where subscripts L and T denote directions parallel and perpendicular to the fibers, respectively, x and y denote the length and width directions of the laminate, respectively, α 's are the thermal expansion coefficients and β 's the moisture swelling coefficients, ΔT is the temperature variation, $C_e(z, t)$ the effective moisture concentration.

For the 90° layers, the stresses can be obtained by interchanging subscripts L and T .

In the absence of mechanical loads the values of ϵ^0 and κ can be determined from the conditions that $N_x(t) = N_y(t) = M_x(t) = M_y(t) = 0$. The resulting expressions read:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x^0(t) = & \frac{h}{\Delta} \{ (Q_L + Q_T) [hP\Delta T(t) + RG(t) + SF(t)] \\ & - Q_{LT}L [hP\Delta T(t) + RF(t) + SG(t)] \} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\epsilon_y^0(t) = \frac{h}{\Delta} \left\{ (Q_L + Q_T) [hP\Delta T(t) + RF(t) + SG(t)] - Q_{LT}L [hP\Delta T(t) + RG(t) + SF(t)] \right\} \quad (20)$$

$$\kappa_x(t) = \kappa_y(t) = 0 \quad (21)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= h^2(Q_L + Q_T)^2 - (Q_{LT}L)^2 & F(t) &= \int_0^h C_e(z,t) dz \\ G(t) &= \int_h^L C_e(z,t) dz & P &= Q_L\alpha_L + Q_{LT}(\alpha_T + \alpha_L) + Q_T\alpha_T \\ R &= Q_L\beta_L + Q_{LT}\beta_T & S &= Q_{LT}\beta_L + Q_T\beta_T & C_e(z,t) &= C(z,t) - C_{th} \end{aligned}$$

C_{th} denotes the threshold moisture concentration below which no swelling effect is observed and h is the common thicknesses of 90° and 0° laminae group, while $-$ as before $-2L$ is the total thickness of the laminate.

Computations were performed with the aforementioned values of C_0 , C_n , β_n ($n = 1, \dots, 7$), with $2L = 0.127$ mm, $E_L = 148$ GPa, $E_T = 11$ GPa and $\nu_{LT} = 0.28$. In addition, we took $\beta_L = 0$, $\beta_T = 3.24 \times 10^{-3}/1\%$ moisture weight gain, $\Delta T = -180^\circ\text{C}$, $\alpha_L = -0.02 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ and $\alpha_T = 27.5 \times 10^{-6}/1^\circ\text{C}$. Also $C_e = C - 0.1\%$.

For purpose of comparison, the lower Fickian data fit employed $C_0 = 1.12 \times 10^{-2}$ and $D = 3.2 \times 10^{-4}$ mm²/hour, while the upper Fickian fit corresponded to $C_0 = 1.32 \times 10^{-2}$ and $D = 1.7 \times 10^{-4}$ mm²/hour. A typical result for the corresponding residual stress profiles is shown in Figure 2.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In principle, the diffusion process of water in polymers and polymeric composites may depart from the idealizations inherent in the classical formulation of Fick. Although there are abundant reasons for that departure, the current work focused on correlating non-Fickian weight gain data with a time-dependent boundary condition, as motivated by the viscoelastic response of polymers.

It is shown that non-Fickian aspects of the moisture absorption process have significant effects on the resulting hygro-thermal stresses in composite materials. The current work reveals the sensitivity of the residual hygro-thermal stresses to a boundary condition of a viscoelastic type, exhibiting discrepancies of about 20 - 30%.

For a diffusion process whose lower and upper Fickian fits can be found, it is safe to say that the residual stresses which correspond to those two cases provide bounds for the non-Fickian case, resulting in good engineering estimates for the residual stresses in laminates.

However, for an accurate assessment, non-Fickian analysis is needed and the formulations presented in this work provide a systematic method to treat this case.

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Figure 1. The total moisture weight gain data and the theoretical predictions by non-Fickian fitting and Fickian fittings with two different saturation levels.

Figure 2. The residual hygro-thermal stress σ_x across the thickness of a $(O_2/90O_2)_8$ laminate at $t = 3600$ hours.